

A review: Synthesis of azachalcone and its biological activity

Aparana Surendra Dighade *

Department of Chemistry, J. D. Patil Sangludkar Mahavidyalaya, Daryapur, Maharashtra, India.

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Abstract

The heterogeneous chemical potential of azachalcone has six-membered motifs containing nitrogen in the ring, leading to active research in their synthetic methodologies. This paper summarizes various methods via aldol reaction, Claisen-Schmidt condensation, molecular hybridization, environmentally trendy microwave-assisted method etc. to acquire azachalcones and their derivatives along with biological activities.

Keywords: Azachalcones; Condensation; Biological activities; Aldol reaction

1. Introduction

Chalcones are a class of naturally occurring compounds with various biological activities.¹ They are known as the precursors of all flavonoid-type natural products in biosynthesis.² Among the various biological activities of chalcones are their insecticidal, antimicrobial, antichinoviral and antipicorniviral, and bacteriostatic properties.³ Azachalcones (the derivatives of chalcones with an annular nitrogen atom in the phenyl ring). Have also been reported to have wide variety of biological activities such as antibacterial, anti-tubercular, and anti-inflammatory potential³.

Heterocycles are abundant in nature and significant to life because their structural subunits exist in many natural products such as vitamins, hormones, and antibiotics. etc⁴ they have attracted considerable attention in the design of biologically active molecules.⁵ Azachalcones are not naturally occurring compounds.⁶ The most common strategy for the synthesis of chalcones is Claisen-Schmidt condensation.⁷⁻⁸ A practical method for the synthesis of such compounds is of great interest in synthetic organic chemistry.

Azachalcone is another class of the chalcone family in which the carbons of either rings A or B or both were replaced with a nitrogen atom. Because of their structural similarity, azachalcones were synthesized with the same strategy as chalcones, in which the substituted acetophenone was replaced with 2-acetyl pyridine.⁹⁻¹⁰

Chalcone

Azachalcone

Structure of chalcone and azachalcone

* Corresponding author: Aparana Surendra Dighade

1.1. Synthesis of Azachalcone Derivatives

Nur Rohman¹¹ focuses on crafting azachalcone derivatives from 2-acetylpyridine and aromatic aldehydes using l-proline/Et₃N as a catalyst. Refinements encompass catalyst dosage, solvents, temperature, and post-reaction treatments and show significant antioxidant potency with inhibition.

Jefferson R reported¹² twenty-four heterocyclic amine-azachalcones compounds through molecular hybridization of chalcone scaffold and fragments of isoniazid, fluoroquinolones, and linezolid with antituberculosis potential

Mohammed Abed Kadhim¹³ synthesized novel Azachalcone compounds that were prepared by the reaction of 3-acetylpyridine with different aromatic aldehyde.

Canan Albay¹⁴ The convenient approach for the synthesis of *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-methoxy (*E*)-2-, -3-, and 4-azachalcones (1-9) involves the Claisen-Schmidt condensation of methoxy-substituted aryl methyl ketones with pyridine carboxaldehyde with 3 equivalents of Na₂CO₃ solution (EtOH, 95%), which yields the *trans* isomer of the corresponding α,β -unsaturated ($J = 15.4/16.8$ Hz, respectively) compounds (1-9)

Asu Usta¹⁵ Two new azachalcones prepared by both Claisen-Schmidt condensation and simple environmentally friendly microwave-assisted method. Ten new N-alkyl substituted azachalconium bromide were prepared from compounds 1 and 2 with corresponding alkyl halides. The antimicrobial activity of all the compounds was tested against *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Yersinia pseudotuberculosis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* microorganism.

ze zang¹⁶ Michael addition reaction of chalcone and azachalcone with ethyl acetoacetate has been successfully performed in the presence of the catalytic amount of (K_2CO_3 10 mole %) and under the high-speed vibrational milling condition the reaction takes place at ambient temperature without any solvent and full completion can be achieved in a very short time (22-40 min) in the most cases conventional side reaction were avoided.

Eleni Hadjikyprianou¹⁷ reported thirteen (13) azachalcone dienophiles with various substituents (1a-m, Scheme S1, Supporting Information) were synthesized via aldol reaction of the corresponding aromatic aldehydes with an enolate generated from 2-acetylpyridine under basic conditions, followed by in situ dehydration.

Tzeng-Lien Shih¹⁸ A series of B-ring, halo-substituted chalcones and azachalcones were synthesized to evaluate and compare their anti-inflammatory activity.

A novel and efficient direct aldol condensation from various ketones and a wide range of aldehydes was catalyzed by L-proline-TEA (triethylamine) in MeOH at room temperature, affording the corresponding (*E*)- α,β -unsaturated ketones¹⁹.

A potent inhibitor of polyphenol oxidase and their structure-activity relationships are described. Azachalcone derivatives were synthesized and tested for their tyrosinase inhibitory activity. Their inhibitory activities on mushroom tyrosinase using L-DOPA as a substrate were investigated²⁰.

New N-substituted derivatives of 3-azachalcone of potential antimicrobial activity.²¹ Synthesis and antimicrobial properties of N-substituted derivatives of (E)-4-azachalcones.²²

1.2. Biological Activity of Azachalcone

Chalcones (1,3-diphenyl-2-propen-1-ones) are key precursors in the synthesis of a large array of biologically important heterocycles (azachalcones).^{23,24} Thus, the synthesis of azachalcones has generated vast interest among organic and medicinal chemists. Chalcones and their heterocyclic analogs (azachalcones) display a wide range of biological activities, such as anticancer,²⁵ antimutagenic,²⁶ anti-inflammatory,²⁷ antituberculosis,²⁸ antimalarial,^{29,30} antileishmanial,^{31,32} nitric oxide regulation modulatory,³³ cardiovascular,³⁴ cell differentiation inducing³⁵ and antihyperglycemic,³⁶ activities.

Nur Rohman¹¹ focuses on crafting azachalcone shows significant antioxidant potency with inhibition. Heterocyclic amine-azachalcones compounds through molecular hybridization with antituberculosis potential¹². azachalcones prepared by both claisen- Schmidt condensation with antimicrobial activity,¹⁵ anti-inflammatory activity,¹⁸

Studies have shown that azachalcones possess anti-bacterial, anti-inflammatory, and anti-cancer properties.³⁷⁻⁴⁰ Recent reports⁴¹ aimed at chalcones as compounds with a wide range of biological activities such as anticancer, cancer-preventative effects, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antidiabetic, antioxidant, antimicrobial, antiviral, antimalarial, and neuroprotective effects. Many studies showed other structural combinations, aiming for new antitubercular agents, as seen in chalcones^{42,43} by the use of creative and intuitive molecular hybridization approach.

Structure of new antitubercular agents

2. Conclusion

Author should provide an appropriate conclusion to the article. Write a conclusion as a single para. Conclusion should be concise, informative and can be started with summarizing the outcome of the study in 1-2 sentences and end with one line stating: how this study will benefit the society and the way forward

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